

Hey there! 🙌

Missed us? We have certainly missed you!

These past few months have been non-stop at FOODITY. It has been an intense but rewarding period as we have completed the first year of our three-year endeavour.

Three of our key milestones:

- After successfully launching our **Open Call #1**, [receiving over 100 submissions](#), we have selected our [first batch of FOODITY innovators](#): six groundbreaking projects now participating in our Pilot Development Programme to scale their solutions.
- We have developed a robust **data management architecture** to protect and properly store data, which our FOODITY innovators will use as part of their projects. The ***datalake*** for storing data and the ***dataU*** for processing and managing it.
- We have started **engaging citizens** through interviews and workshops that we have carried out in different hubs across Europe, from [Austria](#) to [Portugal](#) via [Bulgaria](#), to discuss data privacy and sovereignty in food and nutrition.

Now, are you ready to join us in revolutionising food systems, prioritising health, sustainability, and data sovereignty? If so, we have exciting news:

[Our second call for proposals to fund data-driven solutions for food and nutrition is now open!](#)

Apply to FOODITY Open Call #2!

- Looking for startups/SMEs, social innovators, researchers, and training organisations.
- Solutions in shopping experiences, education or services – or an open challenge.
- Opt to receive up to €187.500, tailored mentoring, training and technical support.

Deadline: 10 July 2024

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FOODITY

In our mission to create a **dynamic ecosystem of digital solutions for food and nutrition that respect citizens' rights to personal data sovereignty**, we are committed to helping the innovators reshaping our food systems — making a positive impact for people and the planet.

We will fund (with up to €187,500) six data-driven initiatives aimed at boosting innovation in food and nutrition and enable citizens to have control over their data.

These solutions will empower their users to make better — healthier and more environmentally friendly — dietary decisions, thus contributing to creating more sustainable food systems.

Selected beneficiaries will also receive **tailored mentoring, training and technical support** over 12 months to develop their products and services and prepare to enter the market.

Startups/SMEs, social innovators, RTOs and universities, and training organisations — with technical, social innovation, and citizen engagement expertise — are welcomed to submit proposals focusing on one of our themes — shopping experiences, education or services — or an open challenge.

Are you up for the challenge?

Apply by 10 July 2024

Learn how to apply

Sign up for our **online events** to learn the keys to this opportunity and solve all your questions about it.

FOODITY and DRG4FOOD Matchmaking Event

23 May 2024, 3:00 pm CET

There's still time to register! Join us to connect with leading researchers and innovative startups, and find partners to apply for our Open Call.

[Sign up now](#)

Info Webinar #1: Keys to FOODITY Open Call #2

Learn more about the key aspects of our Open Call #2 (goals, eligibility, how to apply, data architecture) and about the Open Call #2 of DRG4FOOD, our sister project, which will support trustworthy data-driven innovations in key areas of the food sector.

[Press play](#)

**We will celebrate our next info webinar on 18 June 2024, stay tuned to our channels to sign up!*

Social Innovation Actors

Are you a social innovator and want to find partners to apply?

Complete the form below with your organisation's key information. We will showcase it on our website so other organisations can contact you to collaborate on a joint proposal.

Fill in the form

Open Call for Evaluators

Join us as an external evaluator

We have just launched an open call for external evaluators! Apply to join our pool of experts and participate in the selection of the applications we receive for our Open Call #2 (you will be reimbursed for your effort).

Apply by 12 June

Be inspired by our
Open Call #1

innovators

Six multidisciplinary teams from across Europe committed to transforming our food systems through data-driven innovation.

CSE-TKAS, The Kitchen Adventure

They aim to encourage behaviour change and contribute to a healthy and sustainable nutrition through a groundbreaking app.

FoodMarketMap

They are focused on enhancing shopping experiences and promoting personalised nutrition and sustainable food systems through their Eatvisor app.

Stay tuned to our channels to follow their innovation journey!

Contact us

Your feedback is a gift to us!

Enjoy reading?

Forward this newsletter to a friend.

Keep up to date with our news!

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